

SUPPORTING DATA FOR THE FOLLOWING PAPER PUBLISHED
IN THE JOURNAL OF DAIRY SCIENCE

<https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2020-19985>

**Replacing stearic acid with oleic acid in supplemental fat blends improves
fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows**

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Replacing stearic acid with oleic acid in supplemental fat blends improves fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows. *By Prom and Lock, page XXX.* The objective of our study was to determine the impact of altering the ratio of stearic and oleic acids in a dietary fat supplement on fatty acid digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows. We observed that increasing oleic acid increased digestibility and absorption of total, 16-carbon, and 18-carbon fatty acids. Supplemental fat increased milk yield, milk fat yield, and energy corrected milk, but there was no difference between the fatty acid supplemented treatments. Overall, fatty acid supplementation increased milk yield and energy corrected milk regardless of the ratio of stearic to oleic acid. Increasing oleic acid in a dietary fat supplement increased fatty acid digestibility and preformed milk fatty acid yield without negatively affecting dry matter intake.

Supplemental Table S1. Milk fatty acid yields of cows fed treatment diets (n = 8)

Variable	Treatments ¹				SEM	Contrasts ²		
	CON	50:10	40:20	30:30		CON vs FAT	Linear	Quadratic
Selected Individual FA ³ , g/d								
C4:0	33.5	36.9	37.7	37.0	1.52	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
C6:0	25.9	27.4	27.6	26.5	1.03	0.09	0.46	0.05
C8:0	17.2	17.8	17.7	16.7	0.66	0.69	0.37	0.06
C10:0	54.7	54.4	52.8	49.1	2.10	0.09	<0.01	0.19
C12:0	70.8	68.5	64.8	59.8	3.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.46
C14:0	199	200	196	189	7.85	0.36	0.05	0.26
C14:1	15.8	15.0	14.4	13.1	1.36	<0.01	<0.01	0.52
C16:0	510	550	537	523	22.2	0.02	0.54	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	23.9	23.4	22.7	21.1	1.99	0.02	<0.01	0.22
C18:0	89.9	109	111	116	3.61	<0.01	<0.01	0.01
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	2.27	2.84	3.19	3.62	0.13	<0.01	<0.01	0.44
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	1.73	2.11	2.43	2.67	0.14	<0.01	<0.01	0.25
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	3.94	4.49	5.00	5.52	0.37	<0.01	<0.01	0.94
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	6.37	7.20	7.67	7.85	0.57	<0.01	<0.01	0.20
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	218	250	264	264	12.0	<0.01	<0.01	0.01
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	6.98	7.25	7.06	7.13	0.53	0.43	0.74	0.58
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	32.8	34.5	33.7	33.9	1.65	0.13	0.43	0.26
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	5.17	5.28	5.11	5.07	0.24	0.91	0.35	0.49
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	3.95	4.16	4.52	4.29	0.39	0.08	0.09	0.23

¹Treatments were a non-FA supplemented control diet (CON), and 3 diets incorporating FA supplement blends at 1.4% FA (% diet DM) containing (as a % of total FA) 50% stearic and 10% oleic acid (50:10), 40% stearic and 20% oleic acid (40:20), or 30% stearic and 30% oleic acid (30:30).

²*P*-values associated with contrasts: (1) CON vs. FAT [control vs. FA-supplemented diets; (50:10 + 40:20 + 30:30)/3]; 2) the linear effect of *cis*-9 C18:1 inclusion in the supplemental FA blend, and 3) the quadratic effect of *cis*-9 C18:1 inclusion in the supplemental FA blend.

³De novo fatty acids originate from mammary de novo synthesis (<16 carbons), preformed fatty acids originate from extraction from plasma (>16 carbons), and mixed fatty acids originate from both sources (C16:0 plus *cis*-9 C16:1).

Supplemental Table S2. Milk fatty acid concentration of cows fed treatment diets (n = 8)

Variable	Treatments ¹				SEM	Contrasts ²		
	CON	50:10	40:20	30:30		CON vs FAT	Linear	Quadratic
Selected Individual FA ³ , g/100 g FA								
C4:0	2.41	2.49	2.55	2.57	0.09	<0.01	0.15	0.55
C6:0	1.87	1.85	1.87	1.84	0.05	0.59	0.59	0.34
C8:0	1.24	1.21	1.20	1.16	0.04	<0.01	0.02	0.30
C10:0	3.94	3.68	3.58	3.39	0.13	<0.01	<0.01	0.44
C12:0	5.10	4.62	4.40	4.12	0.18	<0.01	<0.01	0.74
C14:0	14.3	13.4	13.2	13.0	0.16	<0.01	<0.01	0.82
C14:1	1.13	1.00	0.98	0.89	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	0.28
C16:0	36.7	36.9	36.2	36.1	0.67	0.29	<0.01	0.25
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.70	1.56	1.53	1.44	0.11	<0.01	<0.01	0.29
C18:0	6.52	7.37	7.54	7.76	0.37	<0.01	0.03	0.85
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	0.16	0.19	0.22	0.25	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.54
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.12	0.14	0.16	0.18	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.88
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.28	0.30	0.34	0.38	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.87
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.46	0.49	0.52	0.54	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	0.61
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	15.7	16.8	17.8	18.1	0.41	<0.01	<0.01	0.20
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	0.50	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.03	0.17	0.71	0.46
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	2.35	2.33	2.29	2.35	0.09	0.38	0.63	0.25
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	0.37	0.36	0.35	0.35	0.01	<0.01	0.70	0.27
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	0.28	0.28	0.31	0.29	0.02	0.48	0.39	0.10

¹Treatments were a non-FA supplemented control diet (CON), and 3 diets incorporating FA supplement blends at 1.4% FA (% diet DM) containing (as a % of total FA) 50% stearic and 10% oleic acid (50:10), 40% stearic and 20% oleic acid (40:20), or 30% stearic and 30% oleic acid (30:30).

²*P*-values associated with contrasts: (1) CON vs. FAT [control vs. FA-supplemented diets; (50:10 + 40:20 + 30:30)/3]; 2) the linear effect of *cis*-9 C18:1 inclusion in the supplemental FA blend, and 3) the quadratic effect of *cis*-9 C18:1 inclusion in the supplemental FA blend.

³De novo fatty acids originate from mammary de novo synthesis (<16 carbons), preformed fatty acids originate from extraction from plasma (>16 carbons), and mixed fatty acids originate from both sources (C16:0 plus *cis*-9 C16).